

IMPROVEMENT IN UNSTEADY WAKE PREDICTION THROUGH MACHINE LEARNING BASED RANS MODEL TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

The inability of RANS to correctly capture profile wake dynamics and decay prevents the accurate prediction of unsteady losses and poses additional challenges to the aeromechanic verification of both turbines and compressors. This paper addresses this problem by introducing a novel technique applied to improve wake prediction through a RANS based calculation. In particular, for the first time, a data-driven approach is used to develop bespoke turbulence closures to be used in the context of unsteady RANS (URANS) calculations. The new closure is obtained from an evolutionary machine learning algorithm. The algorithm requires a high-fidelity dataset which, in this study, is provided through a DNS for the wake downstream of a normal flat plate with a Reynolds number = 2,000, based on the freestream velocity and plate height. URANS are conducted with the developed closure and the mean flow statistics are compared with the high-fidelity data. The results from the developed closure show excellent agreement with the reference data. Furthermore, the generalisability of the developed closure is evaluated by considering other flat plate wake data, which differ in both the aspect ratio and the Reynolds number from the case used in this study to develop the closures. The results once again show remarkable improvement compared with the standard URANS.

INTRODUCTION

With the only exception of direct solar energy production, almost any energy conversion system requires a turbomachine. In particular, gas turbines (GT) are used for power generation and propulsion. While GT technology is indeed fairly mature, there is still a significant effort to further improve efficiency and reduce weight and cost by better understanding the highly unsteady nature of the flow in both compressor and turbines. On top of unsteadiness generated by turbulence, the stator-rotor interaction is driven by pressure waves and

mostly wakes which are the well-known cause of unsteady losses [1] and are ultimately responsible for aeromechanics problems. Therefore, it is becoming crucial to predict profile wakes correctly from the early design phases.

Figure 1 Vortex shedding in the profile wake of a T106A section

It is well known that standard RANS models such as the $k - \omega$ SST can produce inaccurate prediction of the wake characteristics resulting from vortex shedding [2], [3]. Various approaches have been adopted to improve models in that context, such as coefficient tuning [4], algebraic stress models [5], [6] and machine learning [7]–[9]. The focus of this work will be to present an approach that uses machine learning (referred to as training from now on) to develop Reynolds stress closures, for unsteady flows, that improve the statistics of interest, such as the mean velocity and Reynolds stress profiles. While the machine learning process has been applied successfully to several steady cases [7], [8], its potential is yet to be investigated for an unsteady flow phenomenon, as witnessed in wake vortex shedding.

This problem is of particular interest for turbomachinery applications due to the unsteady nature of turbine and compressor blade wakes (see Figure 1), where poor prediction of wake profiles and losses have been documented using standard RANS models [10]. There is still a significant reliance on RANS modelling for turbomachinery design, simply because high-fidelity calculations are too expensive for industrial design analyses, even with the growing computational resources.

The approach presented here identifies the shortcomings of the current RANS models and suggests a twofold improvement. First, a non-linear turbulence closure, developed via machine learning, is used in lieu of the standard linear closure i.e. the Boussinesq approximation. The use of the machine learning algorithm for developing the closure is different from the approach adopted for steady flow training [7]. As a result, the novel approach posits further improvement by specifying the length scales associated with vortex shedding to be resolved.

The paper is organised into three sections. First, Methodologies details the existing training process and how the new approach incorporates it. Second, Main Results discusses the numerical setup and presents the application of the novel approach, followed by the results from the developed closure. Then, generalisability of the developed closure is evaluated using other published data at different flow conditions.

NOMENCLATURE

- u_i : Instantaneous velocity field
 \tilde{u}_i : Periodic component of instantaneous velocity field
 u_i'' : Turbulent component of instantaneous velocity field
 τ_{ij} : Reynolds stress tensor
 $k = 0.5(\tau_{ii})$: Turbulent kinetic energy
 $a_{ij} = \frac{\tau_{ij}}{2k} - \frac{\delta_{ij}}{3}$: Non-dimensional anisotropy tensor
 S_{ij} : Mean strain rate tensor
 Ω_{ij} : Mean rotation rate tensor
 $\omega = \epsilon/k$: Specific dissipation rate
 V_{ij}^n : n^{th} tensor basis function
 I_n : n^{th} scalar invariant function
 $f_k = k_u/k$: Ratio of unresolved TKE to total TKE
 $f_\omega = \omega_u/\omega$: Ratio of unresolved specific dissipation rate to total specific dissipation rate

ACRONYMS

- TKE: Turbulence Kinetic Energy
Re: Reynolds number
St: Strouhal number
WGB: Wake Generating Body
GEP: Gene Expression Programming
DNS: Direct Numerical Simulation
RANS: Reynolds-Averaged Navier Stokes
PANS: Partially-Averaged Navier Stokes

METHODOLOGIES

The methodology for improved prediction is described here. A summary of the method is displayed in Figure 2, where the red arrows represent the training approach of

Weatheritt & Sandberg [7] for steady flows, while the blue arrows represent the novel approach. Machine learning algorithms, over the recent years, have taken centre-stage due to the increasing availability of high-fidelity datasets. One such algorithm, the Gene Expression Programming (GEP), has found use in developing non-linear turbulence closures. The most commonly used turbulence closure model is the linear Boussinesq approximation

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_{ij}^{mod} &= \frac{2}{3}k\delta_{ij} - 2\nu_t S_{ij}, \\ a_{ij}^{mod} &= -\frac{\nu_t}{k} S_{ij}.\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

This approximation model is linear because the anisotropy tensor (a_{ij}^{mod}) is directly proportional to the mean strain rate tensor (S_{ij}). The validity of this approximation was tested by Schmitt [11], by computing the alignment of the actual anisotropy (a_{ij}^{ref}) and the mean strain rate, where the alignment of two tensors ($a_{ij}^{ref}, a_{ij}^{mod}$) refers to the angle between the two tensors.

$$\rho_{RS} = \frac{a_{ij}^{ref} a_{ij}^{mod}}{\sqrt{a_{ij}^{ref} a_{ij}^{ref} a_{ij}^{mod} a_{ij}^{mod}}}\quad (2)$$

Figure 2 Schematic of model training

A valid model for the anisotropy would produce alignment values of 1.0, while orthonormal and oppositely aligned models would have alignments of 0.0 and -1.0 respectively. It was observed that for most simple flows, the linear approximation was not valid. Using GEP, then, to generate a well-aligned non-linear turbulence closure is the logical next step. This algorithm, in the standard

training process of Weatheritt & Sandberg [7] creates a non-linear model for the anisotropy (a_{ij}^{xf}) by using a reference anisotropy (a_{ij}^{ref}) from a high-fidelity dataset, such as from a DNS. The model is created by regressing the reference anisotropy through the GEP. The generated model is represented using a set of tensor basis and scalar invariant functions.

$$\begin{aligned} V_{ij}^1 &= \frac{S_{ij}}{\omega}, \\ V_{ij}^2 &= \frac{S_{ik}\Omega_{kj} - \Omega_{ik}S_{kj}}{\omega}, \\ V_{ij}^3 &= \frac{S_{ik}S_{kj}}{\omega} - \frac{\delta_{ij}S_{mn}S_{nm}}{3\omega}, \\ I_1 &= S_{mn}S_{nm}; I_2 = \Omega_{mn}\Omega_{nm}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The obtained model is then added as extra anisotropy to a modified Boussinesq approximation.

$$\tau_{ij}^{mod} = \frac{2}{3}k\delta_{ij} - 2\nu_t S_{ij} + 2ka_{ij}^{xf}. \quad (4)$$

In an *a priori* sense, the alignment for this non-linear approximation can be computed by replacing a_{ij}^{mod} with $a_{ij}^{xf} - V_{ij}^1$, since $\nu_t S_{ij}/k = S_{ij}/\omega$ for the $k-\omega$ SST model.

This approach has been applied for steady RANS calculations with observed improvements [7], [12]. Unsteady flows, such as wakes with vortex shedding, require a different treatment. Vortex shedding is associated with a fixed and deterministic frequency and hence a fixed and deterministic length scale. The developed closure from the anisotropy, with the standard approach, contains the effects of these length scales and while they are not directly responsible for turbulence, the URANS equations resolve these scales as well. This means, the process of vortex shedding is being accounted for twice. We propose a modification to the standard training process where the closure is developed with the anisotropy devoid of the vortex shedding length scales. Thus, the novel approach is composed of three prongs: segregation of length scales, resolution and modelling of the corresponding length scales. The existence of vortex shedding indicates existence of organised wave motion, which can be segregated through the triple decomposition approach of Hussain & Reynolds [13]. This decomposition assumes a split of the instantaneous field

$$u(\mathbf{x}, t) = \bar{u}(\mathbf{x}) + \tilde{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) + u''(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (5)$$

Here, the unsteadiness component \tilde{u} corresponds to the deterministic/periodic component associated with vortex shedding while the u'' component corresponds to the stochastic/turbulence component. Standard Reynolds decomposition combines these two components into u' . Applying this split to the Reynolds stress tensor results in a sum of two tensors (similar decomposition for the anisotropy tensor)

$$\tau_{ij} = \overline{u'_i u'_j} = \overline{\tilde{u}_i \tilde{u}_j} + \overline{u''_i u''_j} = \widetilde{\tau}_{ij} + \tau''_{ij}, \quad (6)$$

where $\widetilde{\tau}_{ij}$ represents the Reynolds stress from the organised unsteadiness and τ''_{ij} represents the Reynolds stress from the turbulent length scales. Assuming a split of this type were possible, the novel approach suggests resolution of the deterministic unsteadiness while modelling the stochastic unsteadiness for improved prediction. The resolution of the length scales can be achieved by considering scale-resolving simulation alternatives, of which, the Partially-Averaged Navier Stokes (PANS) approach of Girimaji [14] is used here. PANS has been chosen over other alternatives for two reasons: similar equations for the turbulence modelling as RANS, i.e. $k_u - \omega_u$ SST and availability of explicit cut-off parameters f_k, f_ω , which can be used to specify the resolution of the vortex shedding length scales. These parameters are defined as:

$$f_k = \frac{k_u}{k}; f_\omega = \frac{\omega_u}{\omega} = \frac{1}{f_k}. \quad (7)$$

The subscript u represents an unresolved/modelled quantity. Using the above definitions for the cut-offs, the equations for k_u, ω_u can be given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial k_u}{\partial t} + U_j \frac{\partial k_u}{\partial x_j} &= P_{k_u} - \beta^* k_u \omega_u + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\frac{v_u}{\sigma_{k_u}} \frac{\partial k_u}{\partial x_j} \right], \\ \frac{\partial \omega_u}{\partial t} + U_j \frac{\partial \omega_u}{\partial x_j} &= \alpha \frac{P_{k_u}}{v_u} \\ &\quad - \left(\alpha \beta^* \frac{k_u}{v_u} - \alpha \beta^* f_k^* \frac{k_u}{v_u} + \beta f_k^* \omega_u \right) \omega_u \\ &\quad + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\frac{v_u}{\sigma_{\omega_u}} \frac{\partial \omega_u}{\partial x_j} \right] \\ &\quad + 2(1 - F_1) \sigma_{\omega 2} \frac{1}{f_k^{*2} \omega_u} \frac{\partial k_u}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial \omega_u}{\partial x_j}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha, \beta, \beta^*, \sigma_k, \sigma_\omega, \sigma_{\omega 2}, CD_{k\omega}$ are the standard blended coefficients from the $k - \omega$ SST model while:

$$v_u = \frac{a_1 k_u}{\max(a_1 \omega_u, SF_2)},$$

$$F_1 = \tanh \left[\left(\min \left[\max \left(\frac{\sqrt{k_u}}{\beta^* \omega_u y}, \frac{500v}{y^2 \omega_u} \right), \frac{4\sigma_{\omega 2} k_u}{y^2 CD_{k\omega}} \right] \right)^4 \right],$$

$$F_2 = \tanh \left[\left[\max \left(\frac{2\sqrt{k_u}}{\beta^* \omega_u y}, \frac{500v}{y^2 \omega_u} \right) \right]^2 \right],$$

$$\sigma_{k_u} = \sigma_k f_k^{*2}; \sigma_{\omega_u} = \sigma_\omega f_k^{*2}.$$

One key difference in current approach is that in the above equations, the cut-off f_k is replaced with f_k^* . The terms differ only in the way they are evaluated, described in the following paragraph. The amount of modelling and consequently resolving is controlled by the value of f_k

which, if equals 1.0, corresponds to modelling of all length scales i.e. RANS and if equals 0.0, corresponds to resolving of all scales i.e. DNS. The usual use of f_k in PANS is either as a fixed value in space and time [15], [16] or fixed in time while varying in space [17]. The spatial variation in PANS studies is grid dependent through

$$f_k \geq \frac{1}{k} \frac{\epsilon}{c_\mu} (\epsilon \Delta)^{\frac{2}{3}}, \quad (8)$$

where, k and ϵ are obtained from a baseline URANS calculation and Δ is the grid size, usually taken to be the maximum cell edge length. The use of f_k in this study, however, differs from the previous studies, with the aim to resolve predetermined length scales, particularly corresponding with vortex shedding. Thus, f_k is extracted from the high-fidelity dataset and is referred to as f_k^* to differentiate from the commonly used f_k in other PANS studies. The extraction of f_k^* is achieved by splitting the Reynolds stress tensor according to split defined in Eqn 6. Splitting of the Reynolds stress is recommended by collecting the time series of the high-fidelity data at a sufficient time interval and obtaining the \tilde{u}_i component by applying a filter of the Gaussian type, centred at the vortex shedding frequency, to the Fourier transformed time series. An inverse transform of the filtered Fourier transform results in \tilde{u}_i , which can be used to reconstruct $\tilde{\tau}_{ij}$. A Gaussian distribution has been chosen over an ideal filter to prevent ringing in the data. With the available $\tilde{\tau}_{ij}$ field, the τ_{ij}'' field can be obtained by subtracting from the time averaged τ_{ij} field. Using this decomposition, the TKE can also be split up into periodic and turbulent contributions. Since the definition of f_k^* is the ratio of unresolved to the total TKE, a parallel may be drawn by comparing the high-fidelity TKE split of periodic and turbulent TKE with the PANS equivalent of resolved and unresolved TKE. The periodic TKE should be the equivalent of the resolved TKE while the turbulent TKE would be the equivalent of the unresolved TKE i.e. $k_u = 0.5\tau_{ii}'' = k''$. So, $f_k^* = k''/k$.

The resultant f_k^* field is spatially varying and is different from the f_k used in other studies in two ways. First, it is obtained from a dataset and second, the spatial distribution is not dependent on the grid. This means that the distribution of f_k^* on different grids remains the same at a given spatial location. The impact of this is that the f_k^* is not tied down to the grid resolution, so, grid refinements beyond an optimal grid resolution will not resolve more structures on account of the fixed spatial f_k^* distribution, whereas a spatial f_k defined by Eqn 8 will change with subsequent refinements and thus the proportion of scales resolved. Spatially varying f_k^* is permissible if dynamic change in it is smaller than that of the turbulence quantities [18]. With the obtained f_k^* , it is important to model only the remaining length scales, which is where the novel approach differs from the standard training process. This is achieved by using only the ‘‘turbulent’’ part of the anisotropy (a_{ij}') to create a model through GEP (a_{ij}^{xt}). This model is then added to a similarly modified Boussinesq

approximation, where the approximation should model only the length scales associated with turbulence.

$$\tau_{ij}^{mod} = \frac{2}{3} k_u \delta_{ij} - 2v_u S_{ij} + 2k_u a_{ij}^{xt}. \quad (9)$$

Note that the model here is constructed using unresolved quantities i.e. k_u, v_u and as such, the Reynolds stress obtained corresponds to the modelled stress only, while the total Reynolds stress would be a sum of this stress and the resolved Reynolds stress i.e. stress resolved by the grid. This sets the novel approach apart from the standard training process, where all the length scales were being modelled through Eqn 4.

MAIN RESULTS

The results section is subdivided into two main parts. First, a demonstration of the methodology discussed in the previous section is presented, through a case study. Second, the developed framework is subjected to the generalisability test by applying the output of the framework to other case studies.

DEMONSTRATION

The case study considered for demonstration is that of a wake generated by a flat plate normal to the flow. Since the aim here is to assess the improvements in wake prediction, a canonical representation is chosen over wake shedding from an LPT or HPT. This eliminates the complexity and the effects of the flow upstream of the blade trailing edge. The flat plate is of height 1 unit, thickness 0.16 units and is subjected to a Reynolds number of 2,000, based on the plate height and upstream velocity. The Re chosen for the study is representative of an LPT Re of 100,000 based on the isentropic exit velocity and chord length, for a blade trailing edge thickness equal to 2% of the chord length.

Figure 3 Schematic of domain considered, with the boundary conditions. NRCBC: Non-reflecting characteristic, ICBC: Integrated characteristic, PBC: Periodic boundary conditions

The resulting wake is allowed to spatially evolve in a zero-pressure gradient environment. The first stage in improving the wake prediction is to generate a high-fidelity dataset. A DNS of this case was conducted using HiPSTAR, the schematic domain of which is shown in

Figure 3. HiPSTAR is a finite difference based compressible Navier-Stokes solver, using a fourth-order accurate spatial and temporal discretisation stencil. The boundaries in the streamwise direction (x) were specified as Integrated Characteristic (ICBC) for inflow and Non-Reflecting Characteristic boundary conditions for outflow (NRCBC) [19], [20]. An additional zonal boundary condition was coupled with the NRCBC to damp reflections back from the outflow [21]. The boundaries in the cross-stream (y) direction were specified as periodic to mimic a blade trailing edge cascade. The domain in the x - y plane extends from -15 to 85 units in x direction and -20 to 20 units in the y direction. The spanwise direction (z) is solved in Fourier space to save computational effort with periodic boundaries. After conducting a domain convergence study, the spanwise extent was limited to 8 units and is comparable to other flat plate DNS studies [22]. Following this, a grid independence study was performed with the optimal grid containing $1,056 \times 396$ points in the x - y plane and 64 Fourier modes in the spanwise direction. The energy spectra for this case are shown in Figure 4, for different streamwise locations. There is a peak in the spectra at location $(x, y) = (10, 2)$ which corresponds to a Strouhal number (St) of 0.145, signalling vortex shedding.

Figure 4 Power spectral density of streamwise velocity at different streamwise locations

To obtain the f_k^* field, 400 time samples of the data were collected at a capturing interval of 0.5 time units such that the total time contained ~ 29 vortex shedding cycles for the observed St . The time series was Fourier transformed to frequency space and a Gaussian filter centred at the vortex shedding frequency was applied. The inverse Fourier transform of the field resulted in obtaining the \tilde{u}_i field. This allowed a construction of $\tilde{\tau}_{ij}$ and consequently f_k^* following the discussion in the previous section. The resulting field is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 f_k^* field from DNS dataset

Nearer to the WGB, the value of f_k^* is smaller than 1.0 and increases progressively downstream. Beyond $x = 20.0$, the value of f_k^* is ~ 1.0 . This distribution signals increased presence of turbulence for $x > 20.0$, while for $x < 20.0$, the proportion of periodic and turbulent scales are comparable. This can also be verified from the turbulence energy spectra at different locations. The vortex shedding peak is visible only for $(x, y) = (10.0, 2.0)$ but not for locations beyond $x = 20.0$.

This distribution represents a large contribution to the TKE from the vortex shedding length scales close to the WGB and is consistent with the energy spectra in Figure 4. Following this, the non-linear closures were developed for the two approaches using a_{ij} for the standard training process and a_{ij}'' for the novel training approach, obtained from the DNS dataset. In this study, an outline of the training process is provided but for further details, the reader is referred to Weatheritt & Sandberg [7]. The model is generated through tensorial regression, where an initial population of models are generated, based on a random number generator. The fitness of these models are evaluated through a cost function, the objective of which is to reduce the error between the model anisotropy and the reference anisotropy provided. Successive iterations evaluate the error in the current population of models, discarding those that are above a threshold and replacing those with low error models with mutation i.e. modified coefficients of the different tensor basis functions. This iterative approach drives to a final model with the lowest possible error. In this study, the GEP algorithm was run 50 times with different initialisation for both the approaches and the error values of all the resulting non-linear models were plotted on a histogram (not shown here).

The final models for the two approaches are taken by computing the arithmetic average of all models that fall within the most frequently occurring brackets given by:

$$a_{ij}^{xf} = 0.872V_{ij}^1 + (0.0037 + 0.00053I_1 - 0.00028I_2)V_{ij}^2 + 0.032V_{ij}^3$$

$$a_{ij}^{xt} = 0.869V_{ij}^1 + 0.003V_{ij}^2 + (0.008 - 0.000034I_2)V_{ij}^3$$

Figure 6 (from top to bottom) Alignment for the Boussinesq approximation, model for the standard training and model for the novel training approach. The range has been clipped from -1.0 to 0.0 since no values in this range exist.

These models show that the dominant tensor basis function is V_{ij}^1 , i.e. the mean strain rate tensor. This term is responsible for adding turbulent diffusion, with large negative coefficients adding more diffusion and vice versa. Since the models here are added as extra anisotropies to the Boussinesq approximation, the effective coefficients for the two models are -0.128 and -0.131, while the standard Boussinesq approximation has a coefficient of -

1.0. This suggests that the actual turbulent diffusion for improved prediction should be ~ 8 times smaller than what the Boussinesq approximation provides. This significant reduction of course is only meaningful in the context of unsteady RANS, provided that a large part of the unsteadiness is resolved.

Figure 7 Q-criterion for the baseline URANS (top) and trained PANS (bottom), highlighting scale resolution

The quality of the two models can be compared with the Boussinesq approximation by computing the alignment, shown in Figure 6. The terms in the brackets represent the term a_{ij}^{mod} in the formula for alignment i.e. $-V_{ij}^1$ for the Boussinesq, $a_{ij}^{xf} - V_{ij}^1$ for the standard approach and $a_{ij}^{xt} - V_{ij}^1$ for the novel approach. The alignment plots have been clipped to show values between 0.0 and 1.0, which accentuates the regions of poor alignment and also because there were no alignment values between -1.0 and 0.0.

The alignment for all models is good for $x > 20.0$. This is because the wake evolution is governed by shear in regions of pure turbulence, for which the Boussinesq approximation was primarily developed. In regions dominated by the coherent structures of vortex shedding, the Boussinesq approximation provides poor values of alignment in the range of 0.4 and 0.6. The standard training process improves the alignment slightly for these locations i.e. $x < 20.0$, while the new approach shows even better alignment values for these locations. This suggests that running calculations with these models should show an improvement over the standard URANS.

The calculations were performed in OpenFOAM, where the standard $k - \omega$ SST model was converted into the PANS equivalent $k_u - \omega_u$ SST model. The same domain extents in the x - y plane were used as in the DNS, with 672×290 in-plane points and a spanwise extent of 4 units with 32 points.

Figure 8 Mean velocity, shear stress & TKE at $x = 30.0$

The spanwise extent was chosen based on other PANS studies [23], [24]. The grid resolution was chosen after performing a grid independence test where it was found that the chosen resolution produced comparable mean flow with calculations on the DNS grid resolution. As discussed in the Methodologies, a grid independence study is possible in the context of PANS here since the cut-off f_k^* is not dependent on the grid unlike in Eqn 8.

Figure 9 Centreline profiles for mean velocity and TKE

Three calculations are discussed in the following, the URANS untrained (labelled U-UT), which is the standard $k - \omega$ SST model with the Boussinesq approximation closure, the URANS trained (labelled U-T), which is the standard $k - \omega$ SST model with the modified closure using a_{ij}^{xt} and the PANS trained (labelled P-T), which is the $k_u - \omega_u$ SST model with the modified closure using a_{ij}^{xt} . The f_k^* field is provided as an input to the solver (Figure 5). Even though the diffusion coefficients in a_{ij}^{xf} and a_{ij}^{xt} are similar, the URANS trained calculations are performed with a_{ij}^{xt} since the vortex shedding is resolved by the URANS and supplementing the turbulence closure with a model that includes the effects of the vortex

shedding length scales would amount to accounting for these scales twice. A qualitative comparison of the flow using the Q-criterion for the baseline URANS and PANS trained case is shown in Figure 7, which highlights the resolution of scales, visible through the inherent three-dimensionality of the field. This resolution is also observed in the U-T case (Q-criterion not shown here), which can be attributed to the modified turbulent diffusion of the model. The turbulent diffusion in the non-linear model is significantly lower than in the Boussinesq approximation, which allows instabilities in the spanwise direction to develop, resulting in the breakdown of the spanwise rollers.

The statistics such as the mean velocity, TKE and shear stress show improvements consequently. Figure 8 shows the mean velocity, shear stress and TKE at the downstream location $x = 30.0$. The standard URANS (U-UT) shows an overprediction in all the quantities. The trained calculations however, show a remarkable match in the velocity and shear stress and outperform U-UT. Between the two trained models, the P-T shows a better match with the DNS in the velocity and TKE profile. A better representation of the improvements achieved can be seen by comparing the centreline trends, shown in Figure 9 for the mean velocity and mean TKE. Compared with U-UT, the trained models show better overall trends at all streamwise locations. The P-T results do improve the prediction further than with the U-T results, particularly in capturing the recirculation bubble and at locations further downstream.

GENERALISABILITY

A test of generalisability of the developed turbulence closure is to apply it to a different yet similar flow. Two case studies are considered for this demonstration. These case studies are different in the Reynolds number and the thickness of the plate used. The first case in consideration is that of a normal flat plate wake DNS study conducted by Narasimhamurthy & Andersson [25]. The thickness and Reynolds number adopted in the study were 0.02 and 750 respectively as opposed to 0.16 and 2,000 used to develop the new closures. The Strouhal number of the vortex shedding was also different at 0.168 compared with 0.145. The second case considered is the experiment of Kiya & Matsumura [26], with a flat plate of height 20 mm and thickness 4.3 mm, at a Reynolds number of 23,000, based on plate height and freestream velocity. Non-dimensionalising the plate dimensions by the height results in the plate thickness of 0.215.

To evaluate the re-usability of the developed models, the grid resolution and the f_k^* field were left unchanged. First, the results of the Narasimhamurthy & Andersson [25] study are compared with the results from the developed models. Figure 10 shows the mean profiles of the velocity, TKE and shear stress at $x/h = 3.0$, where h is the height of the flat plate. The baseline URANS (U-UT) shows an overprediction of the velocity profile, while the two trained models show considerable improvement. Between the two models, the URANS trained (U-T) model shows slightly better agreement with the DNS results.

Figure 10 Profiles at $x/h = 3.0$ for (top) mean velocity (middle) TKE (bottom) Shear stress compared with DNS [25]

Figure 11 Comparison of the centreline variation in mean streamwise velocity and TKE with the DNS results [25]

Figure 12 Mean velocity profile comparison at $x/h = 8.0$ with experiment [26]

However, this is true for select locations only, such as the one shown. To assess the overall spatial trend, the centreline profiles for mean velocity and TKE are shown in Figure 11.

These results indicate that the PANS trained (P-T) model captures the overall centreline trend better than U-T, including the recirculation bubble. There is some underprediction in the TKE value, particularly close to the flat plate but the overall agreement with the DNS is very good.

The developed models were compared next with the experimental results of Kiya & Matsumura [26]. Figure 12 shows the mean velocity profile for $x/h = 8.0$. The baseline URANS results are also plotted to show the improvements achieved. Once again, U-UT fails to accurately capture the velocity profiles while the trained model shows a sizable improvement over the baseline.

However, both trained models overpredict the velocity deficit. There could be several reasons for this, some of which would require further investigation. First, the trained model and the f_k^* field applied for the calculation was developed for a different Re number, in this case, an order of magnitude lower. Even so, the obtained result suggests the models are robust to a large change in Re. Second, a separate grid independence test might also be required, given the high Re. However, while the final grid may affect the absolute values of the mean profiles, relative to one another, the trained models would still outperform the untrained calculation. Finally, purely based on the velocity profiles obtained, lower turbulent diffusion, by way of reducing the V_{ij}^1 coefficient even further, may provide better results. However, the computational cost of such a venture may increase, due to the larger proportion of scale resolution sought.

Based on the results obtained in the two studies considered, the test for general use of the developed models shows promise. There is a significant improvement achieved when compared with standard URANS, for the different Re considered, even if the results don't fit exactly onto the DNS/experimental results. Best results can be obtained if developed closures are applied to cases that do not differ significantly.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

Growing availability of high-fidelity datasets has led to increased interest in machine learning for training new turbulence closures, thereby improving predictive capability of RANS models. In this study, a novel approach was presented, to improve prediction of unsteady wakes which exhibit vortex shedding. Such phenomenon has a strong engineering relevance as it takes place in turbines with thick trailing edges, in compressors operated off-design, in combustor swirlers, and whenever it is necessary to place struts in the main flow path due to mechanical or auxiliary system requirements.

The approach relied on developing non-linear turbulence closures through an evolutionary machine learning algorithm. The development of these closures is performed by considering anisotropy only from the stochastic length scales, which differs from the standard machine learning based closure development, where the anisotropy resulting from all length scales was used. This modification to the training process is proposed so that the resulting non-linear closure is a true representation of the

turbulence. Further improvements were suggested by resolving the scales not associated with turbulence, i.e. the vortex shedding length scales. This was achieved by implementing a PANS solver which dictated the selective scales for resolution through an input cut-off parameter f_k^* , obtained from the high-fidelity dataset. The results from the trained models show a remarkable improvement, compared with the standard URANS calculation and the extra resolution of scales combined with a trained model provides further improvements in all mean flow statistics. The developed model was then tested for general use on other wake flow case studies, which differed in the thickness of the plate and the Reynolds number. The trends observed from the trained models were highly promising, with all-around improvement observed compared with the standard URANS. Finally, the computational cost, in terms of the core-hours, associated with the two 3D trained calculations were found to be similar, i.e., there was no significant overhead when using PANS over URANS.

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REFERENCES

- [1] V. Michelassi, L. Chen, R. Pichler, R. Sandberg, and R. Bhaskaran, "High-fidelity simulations of low-pressure turbines: Effect of flow coefficient and reduced frequency on losses," *Proc. ASME Turbo Expo*, vol. 2C, no. November 2016, pp. 1–12, 2015.
- [2] M. J. Tummers, D. M. Passchier, and R. A. W. M. Henkes, "Experimental investigation of an adverse pressure gradient wake and comparison with calculations," *Exp. Therm. Fluid Sci.*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 17–24, 1997.
- [3] R. Hoffenberg and J. Sullivan, "Measurement and simulation of wake deceleration," *36th AIAA Aerosp. Sci. Meet. Exhib.*, no. 800, 1998.
- [4] T. J. Praisner, J. P. Clark, T. C. Nash, M. J. Rice, and E. A. Grover, "Performance Impacts due to Wake Mixing in Axial-Flow Turbomachinery," *ASME Turbo Expo 2006*, pp. 1–10, 2006.
- [5] S. Wallin and A. V. Johansson, "An explicit algebraic Reynolds stress model for incompressible and compressible turbulent flows," *J. Fluid Mech.*, vol. 403, pp. 89–132, 2000.
- [6] S. B. Pope, "A more general effective-viscosity hypothesis," *J. Fluid Mech.*, vol. 72, no. 2, pp. 331–340, 1975.
- [7] J. Weatheritt and R. Sandberg, "A novel evolutionary algorithm applied to algebraic modifications of the RANS stress-strain relationship," *J. Comput. Phys.*, vol. 325, pp. 22–37, 2016.
- [8] J. Weatheritt, R. D. Sandberg, G. Laskowski, and V. Michelassi, "Machine Learning For Turbulence Model Development Using A High-Fidelity HPT Cascade Simulation," *Turbomach. Tech. Conf. Expo. GT2017*, 2017.
- [9] K. Duraisamy, G. Iaccarino, and H. Xiao, "Turbulence Modeling in the Age of Data," *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.*, no. April, 2018.
- [10] R. Pichler, J. Kopriva, G. Laskowski, V. Michelassi, and R. Sandberg, "Highly Resolved LES of a Linear HPT Vane Cascade Using Structured and Unstructured Codes," *Turbomach. Tech. Conf. Expo. GT2016*, pp. 1–10, 2016.
- [11] F. G. Schmitt, "About Boussinesq's turbulent viscosity hypothesis: historical remarks and a direct evaluation of its validity," *Comptes Rendus - Mec.*, vol. 335, no. 9–10, pp. 617–627, 2007.
- [12] J. Weatheritt and R. D. Sandberg, "The development of algebraic stress models using a novel evolutionary algorithm," *Int. J. Heat Fluid Flow*, vol. 68, pp. 298–318, 2017.
- [13] A. K. M. F. Hussain and W. C. Reynolds, "The mechanics of an organized wave in turbulent shear flow," *J. Fluid Mech.*, vol. 41, no. 02, pp. 241–258, 1970.
- [14] S. S. Girimaji, "Partially-Averaged Navier-Stokes Model for Turbulence: A Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes to Direct Numerical Simulation Bridging Method," *J. Appl. Mech.*, vol. 73, no. 3, p. 413, 2006.
- [15] F. S. Pereira, G. Vaz, L. Eça, and S. S. Girimaji, "Simulation of the flow around a circular cylinder at $Re=3900$ with Partially-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations," *Int. J. Heat Fluid Flow*, vol. 69, no. December 2016, pp. 234–246, 2018.
- [16] B. Akula, P. Roy, P. Razi, S. Anderson, and S. Girimaji, "Partially-Averaged Navier-Stokes (PANS) Simulations of Lid-Driven Cavity Flow—Part 1: Comparison with URANS and LES," in *Progress in Hybrid RANS-LES Modelling*, vol. 130, 2015, pp. 359–369.
- [17] D. Luo, C. Yan, H. Liu, and R. Zhao, "Comparative assessment of PANS and DES for simulation of flow past a circular cylinder," *J. Wind Eng. Ind. Aerodyn.*, vol. 134, pp. 65–77, 2014.
- [18] B. Basara, S. Krajnovic, S. Girimaji, and Z. Pavlovic, "Near-Wall Formulation of the Partially Averaged Navier Stokes Turbulence Model," *AIAA J.*, vol. 49, no. 12, pp. 2627–2636, 2011.
- [19] J. W. Kim and D. J. Lee, "Generalized Characteristic Boundary Conditions for Computational Aeroacoustics, Part 2," *AIAA J.*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 47–57, 2004.
- [20] J. W. Kim and D. J. Lee, "Generalized Characteristic Boundary Conditions for Computational Aeroacoustics," *AIAA J.*, vol. 38, no. 11, pp. 2040–2049, 2000.
- [21] R. D. Sandberg and N. D. Sandham, "Nonreflecting Zonal Characteristic Boundary Condition for Direct Numerical Simulation of Aerodynamic Sound," *AIAA J.*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp.

- 402–405, 2006.
- [22] A. Hemmati, D. H. Wood, and R. J. Martinuzzi, “Characteristics of distinct flow regimes in the wake of an infinite span normal thin flat plate,” *Int. J. Heat Fluid Flow*, vol. 62, pp. 423–436, 2016.
- [23] P. Ranjan and A. Dewan, “Partially Averaged Navier Stokes simulation of turbulent heat transfer from a square cylinder,” *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.*, vol. 89, pp. 251–266, 2015.
- [24] S. Lakshmi pathy and V. Togiti, “Assessment of alternative formulations for the specific-dissipation rate in RANS and variable-resolution turbulence models,” in *20th AIAA Computational Fluid Dynamics Conference*, 2011, pp. 1–20.
- [25] V. D. Narasimhamurthy and H. I. Andersson, “Numerical simulation of the turbulent wake behind a normal flat plate,” *Int. J. Heat Fluid Flow*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 1037–1043, 2009.
- [26] M. Kiya and M. Matsumura, “Incoherent turbulence structure in the near wake of a normal plate,” *J. Fluid Mech.*, vol. 190, pp. 343–356, 1988.